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IMPLEMENTATION OF A UNIT-BASED COUNCIL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare industry has continued to face nursing shortages exacerbated by the Covid-19 pandemic, leading many nurses to retire early and/or leave the profession due to burnout and compassion fatigue. Structural empowerment is a concept that has been applied to the healthcare industry with improvements in patient care and outcomes. Unit-based council (UBC) is a form of structural empowerment allowing clinical nurses and nurse leaders to convene and collaborate on making clinical decisions that affect the delivery of nursing care in the specific unit. A retrospective analysis was performed to evaluate the root cause of nursing turnover in an intensive care unit from May 1st, 2021, to June 30th, 2022. A total of 27 registered nurses resigned for a variety of reasons. This quality improvement project is created to address professional development and growth to empower nurses and prevent turnover. Staff nurses were asked to participate in a voluntary survey called Conditions for Work Effectiveness I (CWEQ) before the UBC implementation and three months after initiation. Fifteen participants participated in the initial CWEQ survey distributed in December 2022, which yielded a mean structural empowerment score of 2.55. The post-implementation survey was distributed in February 2023 with 13 participants, and the mean structural empowerment score improved to 3.11. The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant for $p < .001$. Overall mean scores increased from 2.55 to 3.11 after UBC implementation. The UBC is a good start to address professional growth, development, and increased job satisfaction.

Keywords: unit-based council, structural empowerment, shared governance, conditions for work effectiveness, implementation, burnout, and compassion fatigue.

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Introduction

While the healthcare industry has continually faced nursing shortages, the Covid-19 pandemic has caused many nurses to retire early or leave the profession for various reasons, such as burnout and compassion fatigue. Nursing Solutions Inc. (NSI) surveyed over 3000 hospitals across the United States about healthcare turnover, retention, recruitment, and staffing strategies. NSI found that the average cost of turnover for one bedside registered nurse is \$40,038 (Plescia, 2021). While these are average rates, areas with higher salaries, including California, will have a higher cost turnover rate compared to a state like Florida which has a lower salary rate. It is estimated that hospitals will lose an average of \$3.6 million to \$6.5 million a year due to nursing turnover. Franklin Shaffer, a journalist for American Nurses Journal, reported in 2020 that firms with performance-enhancing cultures experienced higher revenue growth, higher employment growth, and higher net income growth compared to firms without a performance-enhancing culture (Shaffer & Curtin, 2020). Hospitals that constantly force staff to mandatory overtime encourage existing staff to think about leaving, have increased turnover, longer patient stays, lower productivity rates, and higher treatment error rates (Stimpfel et al., 2012).

Structural empowerment is an important concept that has been applied to the healthcare industry that has improved patient care and outcomes. When there is a lack of structural empowerment, the staff is less committed to the organization leading to lower patient outcomes (Laschinger et al., 2010). Structural empowerment can be defined in many ways, but it essentially allows individuals to take ownership of their own practice having to say in their day-to-day practices (Laschinger et al., 2010). In the healthcare industry, structural empowerment creates a condition where individuals, including nurses, are able to provide the best outcomes for

their patients within their organization and environment. A form of structural empowerment commonly adopted in nursing is the unit-based council (UBC).

A UBC is a council specific to the unit they practice in for nurses and nursing leaders to convene and work with each other to make clinical decisions that affect the delivery of nursing care in their unit (Larkin et al., 2008). The UBC may evaluate policies and procedures of unit-specific standards, incorporate evidence-based literature into practice, analyze and incorporate new plans for unit quality metrics, and work to develop action plans to decrease turnover rates and increase satisfaction rates (Larkin et al., 2008).

Background

In an acute care hospital in downtown Los Angeles that is a comprehensive stroke and heart attack receiving center that provides 24-hour critical care services, including interventional cardiology, cardiac surgery, neurosurgery, neurological vascular intervention, and in-house intensivist, a thorough retrospective analysis was performed in the critical care departments to identify the root cause of nursing turn over. From May 1st, 2021, to June 30th, 2022, there was a total of 27 registered nurses who resigned for a variety of reasons, voluntarily or involuntarily. The calculated mean years of service to the organization is 5.39 years. The high rates of nursing turnover affect the care provided to patients and the overall department budget negatively.

All employees who departed from the organization were invited to participate in an exit survey. The fully anonymous survey with 36 questions addressing different metrics looks for the root cause of nursing turnover within the organization. The survey covers an array of topics, including job satisfaction, growth and development, service and quality, compensation, and leadership. From June 30th, 2021, to June 30th, 2022, all previous employees were offered a chance to complete the survey, which yielded a total of 13 responses. The highest-rated items

that the organization was doing well-included trust in immediate supervisors with clear communication for the expectation of performance, providing useful feedback on performance, the organization's emphasis on the importance of safety, and flexibility in schedule. The common themes that constantly presented themselves included a lack of encouragement in professional development, the training received to be successful at their current job, and sufficient staff required in the department to handle the workload.

The Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) quality improvement (QI) project created a UBC with the collaboration of management and nursing staff to encourage professional development and improve unit workflows. The project measured nursing empowerment scores every three months as an outcome measure.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project is to implement a UBC in a unit where there is no existing council. The DNP project will be formally active for three months. The UBC, however will continue indefinitely, constantly evolving to meet the unique and specific needs of the unit.

Clinical Significance

While increased workplace performance and job satisfaction are multidimensional, with many factors that may contribute, Structural empowerment has been linked to improved job satisfaction rates and increased workplace performance (Orgambidez & Almeida, 2019). Structural empowerment allows individuals to have an active voice in how they practice allowing nurses not only to take ownership of their own practice but also to address issues affecting patient care that is seen and experienced at the bedside level.

Over the past several years, while the entire world is dealing with the Covid-19 virus, nursing burnout has been on the rise due to the overwhelming demand of a stressful work

environment. In 2018, 31.5% of the over 50,000 surveyed nurses reported leaving their profession due to burnout (Shah et al., 2021). Burnout is defined as a decline in physical, emotional, and psychological energy from work-related stress leading to cynicism toward patients and colleagues with feelings of low self-efficacy (Mudallal et al., 2017). In a time when healthcare workers are asked to do more with fewer resources, the environment created may lead to increased errors such as incorrect medical dosing, increased patient falls, and decreased efficiency (Mudalla et al., 2017). The psychological benefit from structural empowerment will lead to decreased burnout rates equating to lower nursing turnover rates.

Nurses are an integral part of health care. The nursing profession continues to face shortages due to many factors, including nursing burnout, an aging population, insufficient staffing, and a lack of empowerment (Rosseter, 2020). A healthcare organization can not function without nursing. Creating a UBC now allows nurses at the forefront to address critical factors to mitigate turnover rates and increase job satisfaction. This would ultimately improve patient outcomes and save the healthcare organization money.

Supporting Framework

Rosabeth Moss Kanter is a professor at Harvard School of Business specializing in strategy, innovation, and leadership for change and the creator of the theory of structural empowerment framework (Harvard Business School Staff, 2022). An organization's sources of power consist of three "lines." Line of supply refers to the external influence of power that managers have the capacity to bring into the organization, such as resources, money, reward, and prestige. Line of information refers to the managers' need to be informed in an informal and formal sense. Moreover, lastly, lines of support refer to a manager's job parameters needed to

allow for non-ordinary action at the discretion of their judgment, allowing for innovation and risk-taking activities without going through multiple approval processes (Kanter, 1979).

Kanter believes that an organization's performance will increase because of structural empowerment. Through formal and informal channels, the six conditions that are required for empowerment to take place include an opportunity for advancement, access to information, access to support, access to resources, formal power, and informal power (Kanter, 1979).

The theoretical framework takes into consideration formal and informal powers, including increasing efficiency in the workplace, lowering burnout levels, increasing autonomy, and increasing job satisfaction. Creating a UBC allows nurses to take ownership of their practice through formal UBC and informal channels by utilizing support from management, information on current practices, and resources to improve patient care through improving current workflow processes. Support from management gives participants psychological empowerment through greater autonomy in practice, more confidence in practice, and higher meaning to the care that is provided.

Kanter discusses two primary empowerment structures relating to an organization: the structure of power and the structure of opportunity. The most common association of power is formal power or a position of power, such as a nurse manager role, assistant manager, and/or nursing supervisor. Other forms of power are informal powers, such as individuals with powers to influence others, alliances or relationships with colleagues, and/or connections within the organization. The structure of opportunity provides an individual with the opportunities to solve problems that arise in the workplace that affect their practice. Examples of unit-based workflows include work and vacation schedules, daily/nightly work assignment prioritization, and break nurse rotations, just to name a few. The structure of opportunities also looks at unit-specific

metrics and methods to improve, such as patient falls, pressure injuries, ventilator-associated pneumonia rates, and catheter-associated urinary tract infections. The UBC utilizes all the tools of power structures, including information (rates of each metric, root cause analysis reports of specific situations), support (from formal powers such as the nursing director, nursing manager, charge nurse, etc.), and resources (paid time to implement research and application of change process) to problem solve.

Review of Literature

A review of the literature was conducted in preparation for the DNP QI project. The following electronic databases were utilized for relevant publications: PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane. The search terms used were structural empowerment, satisfaction, and shared governance, which yielded a total of seven studies dating from 2013 to 2022. Including all terms in the search, database allowed us to filter articles that were not directly related to the project. The search dates were expanded from five years to ten years due to limitations in research articles to allow for the inclusion of all search terms. **Literature Review Synthesis**

Healthcare organizations are constantly searching for ways to improve patient outcomes and quality of care (Kanninen et al., 2021). A structural empowerment model is not a new concept and has been around for decades; that began in the business sector and was adopted in health care as a systemic organizational model (Al-Hammouri et al., 2020). Healthy work environments, job satisfaction, and quality patient care have often been linked to one another, prompting organizational leaders and nurse managers to develop strategies to improve work environments (Sullivan et al., 2017).

Kanter's theory of structural empowerment is defined as the ability to achieve goals through formal and informal powers and access to information, resources, and opportunities (Al-Hammouri et al., 2020). Employees are more committed to the organization, have a higher sense of accountability, and can better fulfill their job depending on their empowerment (Owen et al., 2018; Sullivan et al., 2017).

Shared governance as applied to nursing, emerged over 40 years ago and has been adopted as a systematic organizational model of empowerment (O'Grady & Clavelle, 2021; Owen et al., 2018). Shared governance is defined as a structural model through which nurses can

express and manage their practice with a higher level of professional autonomy (Sullivan et al., 2017). It is a multidimensional organizational characteristic that encompasses structure and process by which professionals direct, control, and regulate goal-oriented efforts of each other (Owen et al., 2018; Hess, 2017).

There are five basic premises on which the nursing shared governance model is based (O'Grady & Clavelle, 2021). Nursing as a profession operates acts in the best interest of the people that they serve and makes decisions to improve their lives. Licensed professionals are protected by the state and ensure that patients are protected from harm through formal education and regulation of the profession. A nursing professional is accountable for the actions/decisions they make within their role. As such, the profession is obligated to establish and exercise standards and behaviors by its representatives. Each professional body, as represented, such as each state's board of nursing, continues to make decisions regarding the education, quality, competence, and practice related to its profession, which defines the character and work of the clinician and the profession. Furthermore, like many other professional groups such as physicians, pharmacists, engineers, lawyers, etc., nursing has a professional governance structure where vital decisions are made and actions are taken relating to professional obligations, quality, education, and competence (O'Grady & Clavelle, 2021).

The nursing shared governance model was introduced in the 1970s to 1980s with the first known adoption and implementation of a shared governance model beginning at St Joseph's hospital in Atlanta, Georgia; St. Michaels Hospital in Milwaukee, Wisconsin; and Rose Medical Center in Denver, Colorado (Ott & Ross, 2013). The three organizations used principles and concept models from Porter O'Grady, Finnegan, and McDonough's contributions to shared governance (Ott & Ross, 2013; Sullivan et al., 2017).

Since its introduction, many healthcare facilities have adopted structural empowerment through shared governance. The principles of structural empowerment and shared governance structures include equity, ownership, partnership, enhanced communication, and collaboration (Ott & Ross, 2013). The purpose of shared governance shifts the decision for affecting practice from the manager level to the unit level (Sullivan et al., 2017). It allows nurses to take a primary role in clinical practice decisions and implementation (Ott & Ross, 2013). Implementing such a practice has been shown to increase organizational commitment, improve patient outcomes, increase nursing satisfaction, and decrease turnover rates (Bieber & Joachim, 2016; Olender et al., 2020).

The emphasis placed on individual accountability for performance and practice helped overcome many initial challenges when implementing a shared governance model (O'Grady & Clavelle, 2021). The journey to empowerment is not a straight line but a relationship created between managers and staff (Ott & Ross, 2013). Through the journey, nurse managers often become mentors and staff nurses become leaders. While the process may be challenging, professional obligation and engagement resulted in positive outcomes in areas of patient care, safety, and practice.

Shared governance councils comprised nurses on the frontline working to identify QI projects that affect their own practice and influence patient outcomes, along with mentoring nursing leaders, including managers, assistant managers, educators, and specialists (Owen et al., 2018). The nursing practice council shares ideas of the consensus staff, improves communication in the units, and promotes problem identification with resolution ideas using evidence-based practices. Some common examples of projects that have been widely examined are decreasing

rates of catheter-associated urinary tract infections, central line-associated bloodstream infections, pressure injuries, and unit self-scheduling to name a few (Bieber & Joachim, 2016).

Methods

This DNP project uses Kanter's structural empowerment design to implement a UBC in an intensive care unit (ICU) at an acute care hospital. Staff nurses in the critical care departments had an opportunity to participate in the study by completing a fully anonymous survey titled Conditions for Work Effectiveness Questionnaire I [CWEQ] (Appendix G) prior to implementation and three months after the start of UBC. The results of the survey were analyzed using a paired *t*-test.

Setting

The QI project was conducted at a comprehensive stroke and heart attack receiving acute care hospital. The hospital provides 24-hour critical care services with an in-house intensivist, interventional cardiologists, neurosurgeons, and neuro-interventionists. The hospital has a 28-bed ICU and an 11-bed cardiac surgery unit to care for all its critically ill patients. The UBC was created in the intensive care department as a pilot.

Sample

The voluntary UBC was composed of nurses on the specific unit with representation from nursing management. The UBC met at least monthly for an hour, addressing key issues relevant to the specific unit. All practicing nurses in the ICU were able to contribute to topics discussed during council meetings if they decided to. The change in practice affected all individuals practicing in ICU after formal education was provided. The informal leaders driving the change were the nursing staff actively participating in council meetings.

Participants

Fifteen ICU nurses participated in the initial survey, with thirteen ICU nurses participating in the three-month follow-up survey. During the individual meetings, the project

author explained the QI project to each nurse and answered all questions to satisfaction. All participants in the survey were staff nurses. Traveler and registry nurses were included in participation. The nurses were informed of the risks and benefits of their involvement in the project.

Planning the QI Project

The QI project addressed a high need for evaluating and improving issues and care metrics in the ICU. Currently, the critical care department meets once every quarter to discuss policy changes affecting all critical care departments. The critical care meeting is comprised of the critical care medical director, critical care nursing director, intensivist, lead respiratory therapist, pharmacist, physical therapy, and occupational therapy departments, which generally meets for one hour. The collaborative effort with nurse managers and staff nurses to develop the UBC will allow us to better serve the patients by addressing unit-specific challenges.

Informational flyers (Appendix F) were posted within the nursing lounge identifying the purpose of UBC, facts about the CWEQ survey, and meeting details. The informational flyers contained detailed information regarding how to submit suggestions if a staff nurse would not like to participate in the UBC but contribute ideas and suggestions for improvement.

Tools

Heath K. Spence Laschinger is a nurse researcher who has dedicated herself to investigating the impact of nursing work environments on nurse empowerment for professional practice, health, and well-being, and the role of leadership in creating empowering working conditions (Western University Staff, 2022b). Dr. Laschinger was a distinguished professor at Western University in Ontario, Canada. She is also credited with developing the CWEQ survey which builds on Kanter's theory of structural empowerment (Western University Staff, 2022a).

The CWEQ has been utilized in research as a standardized tool to measure the four empowerment dimensions, including access to opportunity, access to resources, access to information, and access to support. The CWEQ also addresses further access to empowerment structures such as formal power and informal power. Laschinger takes Kanter's relationship of concepts in the structural theory of power in organizations and expands it with the workplace empowerment model.

Methods of Evaluation and Data Analysis

The CWEQ measures the level of structural empowerment and global empowerment in 7 subscale categories. The surveys were obtained prior to and three months after implementation to determine whether a UBC would help increase structural empowerment scores among staff nurses.

A paired *t*-test is a statistical method of analysis of two measurements taken from the same individual, object, or related unit (Kent State Staff, 2022). The paired *t*-test helped demonstrate if there is any statistical evidence between the paired observations, such as when evaluating two different mean scores. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether a normal distribution could have produced the differences.

Timeline

The performance improvement project was implemented for three months. However, the UBC led by nurses working on the specific unit with support from management continues to meet monthly to address the needs of the staff and patients in the ICU.

As previously stated, the anonymous paper surveys have no identifying information and are stored in the critical care director's office. The data was transcribed onto a computer that is password and fingerprint protected. Analyzed data is stored on a cloud-based storage solution

that is password-protected cloud and requires a two-factor authenticator for access. Only the principal investigator and critical care director have access to the information.

Ethical Issues

Staff nurses were informed regarding the creation of the UBC and invited to participate. A voluntary and anonymous paper survey was provided before and three months after implementing the UBC. The survey has no identifying information about each participant and is stored securely. The surveys have a consent disclaimer at the start of the survey with the title of the project, information about the project, names of investigators, and duration of the project. The consent stated clearly that there is no compensation for participation. By participating in the survey, the participants give full consent for collecting and evaluating information.

The QI project was discussed at the New Knowledge and Innovation Committee and at the Research Oversight Committee at the organization. The project was deemed a QI project and approved to proceed (Appendix H). The application was submitted to the California State University at Los Angeles (CSULA) for further Institutional Review Board (IRB) review before beginning the evidence-based performance improvement project and approved on November 30th, 2022.

Institutional Review Board Approval

The IRB approval from CSULA was secured before the project commenced at the study facility (Appendix I). The QI project was also presented at the hospital organization's knowledge exchange committee meeting and deemed as a QI project.

Measures

The CWEQ survey measured the level of structural empowerment and global empowerment in seven subscale categories. The surveys obtained before and after

implementation were calculated and evaluated to determine whether a UBC may help increase structural empowerment scores.

A paired *t*-test is a statistical analysis method of two measurements taken from the same individual, object, or related unit (Kent State Staff, 2022). The paired *t*-test helped demonstrate if there is any statistical evidence between the paired observations, such as when evaluating two different mean scores.

Results

The initial steps of the QI project were accomplished in December 2022. After IRB approval was obtained in November 2022, CWEQ surveys were distributed to staff nurses willing to participate, with 15 participants in the initial survey distribution. The first UBC meeting was conducted shortly afterward and continued to meet monthly to discuss unit-specific issues, policies, and procedures with support from management. Follow-up surveys were performed towards the end of February 2023. Mean scores were obtained, and a paired *t*-test was conducted.

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between December 2022 and February 2023 differed significantly from zero. A Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to determine whether the differences in December 2022 and February 2023 could have been produced by a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The Shapiro-Wilk test results were insignificant based on an alpha value of .05, $W = 0.99$, $p = .795$. This result suggests the possibility that a normal distribution produced the differences in December 2022 and February 2023 cannot be ruled out, indicating the normality assumption is met.

Overall mean scores increased from 2.55 to 3.11 over a 3-month period. Across the board, mean scores increased when analyzing subcategories, including access to opportunity, access to resources, access to information, access to support, and outlook of the work setting. Access to opportunities mean increased from 3.1 to 3.7, access to information mean increased from 2.0 to 2.5, access to support increased from 2.3 to 3.1, and access to resources increased from 2.3 to 2.6.

The result of the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(57) = -11.33$, $p < .001$, indicating that UBC improved structural empowerment scores.

This finding suggests that the difference in the mean between December 2022 and February 2023 was significantly different from zero. The mean of December 2022 was significantly lower than that of February 2023. The results are presented in Table 1. A bar plot of the means is presented in Figure 1.

Discussion

Discussion, Limitations, and Implications

This QI project investigated the cause of nursing turnover in an ICU at an acute care hospital in Los Angeles, California. After performing a year retrospective analysis on reasons staff nurses resigned, nursing turnover was due to multifaceted problems stemming from job satisfaction, growth and development, compensation, and leadership. Other factors, including a very active Covid-19 pandemic, early retirement in the nursing field, and burnout, are huge factors in which nurses will change career paths. To address one arm of the multifactorial reasons nurses are resigning, a UBC was created to not only address the needs and challenges of the unit but also promote job satisfaction, growth, and development.

Prior to creating the voluntary UBC, obtaining interest from the nurses on the unit was important to the QI project's success. There needs to be a desire from staff nurses to want to create change aside from working their regular patient care shifts. Furthermore, support from the nursing director and managers is critical in terms of non-productive paid time for UBC members.

The increase in mean empowerment scores from December 2022 to February 2023 demonstrates a positive response and outlook within the department as the staff nurses discussed, planned, and implemented projects that are important to them and the unit. Unit-specific issues such as workflow, staffing, mentorship, and training are some examples of topics that are being discussed and addressed. Having a seat at the table and having a say in how they practice, staff nurses with various years of experience, background, and training allow them to take ownership of patient care and outcomes.

There were several limitations of the QI project. The first limitation is that the UBC has been in effect for a limited amount of time with limited experience in implementing change. The

second limitation of the QI project includes the small number of sample subjects that participated in the survey. The organization was acquired by another healthcare entity and there were a lot of changes happening in terms of streamlining policies and procedures from the parent entity that created an environment where many changes were occurring simultaneously. Sustained change takes time and the benefits of a UBC are usually seen long-term in terms of nursing turnover rates, empowerment scores, job satisfaction, and improved patient outcomes. The project lays the groundwork for building a shared governance model in the workplace where staff nurses can learn to become leaders. The change from a top-down approach to a shared governance model requires administration and staff nurses to adapt and grow. The UBC is an investment in staff development to be better prepared to care for patients with all types of diseases and conditions. The success of the UBC depends on the nursing director and nurses on the unit continuing as partnership and mentorship to work on unit-specific issues. While the roles initially may be uncomfortable and different from what was previously practiced in terms of how decisions were being made, embracing professional staff nurses to achieve a higher quality practice are the beginning steps to change for the better.

Recommendations

Changing a department and/or organization's culture takes time. Practices that have been developed through the years will take years to break. Structural empowerment is a commitment made by management and staff to work towards it. The organization must embody the concept in all aspects and how it operates, including hiring, and decision-making. The beginning phase of each project is the most challenging because the organization is treading new waters and stepping out of its comfort zone. The framework developed in this QI project would help the organization if different departments were to choose to start their own UBC.

A UBC is not the only way to encourage structural empowerment in a workplace. Understanding each staff nurse's motivations, strengths/weaknesses, and professional goals allows managers to develop, mentor, and guide through their time with the organization. Other forms of structural empowerment include encouraging staff to develop a staff education program or guiding new graduate nurses through a transition into the practice phase. Opportunities with independent decision-making empower a person to take ownership of their practice. The manager's role in structural empowerment develops into a mentor role through guidance and advocacy.

Conclusions

Addressing nursing turnover is a challenge that the healthcare industry continues to face. The multifaceted problem continues to plague organizations, especially in attracting and retaining staff. The interventions used in this DNP QI project address one aspect of nursing turnover. The project brought to light a problem that the department was facing, obtained data to ensure it was indeed a problem, performed a succinct literature review on current evidence-based practices, implemented a solution, and tracked its progress over time. The stepwise approach ensured that each intervention was made based upon and backed up by data and the most current evidence-based practices.

Based upon the CWEQ and nursing empowerment scores, the UBC is a good start in addressing one factor of nursing turnover rates through professional growth and job satisfaction. The UBC will continue to face a vast of organizational challenges, such as budget restrictions and nursing union factors, such as wage and benefits limitations. Through investment in its staff, the organization's leaders, including administrators and empowered staff will lead in creating change and improving patient outcomes.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Kanter's Relationship of Concepts

Figure 1

Kanter's Relationship of Concepts

Appendix B

Figure 2: Expanded Workplace Empowerment Model

Figure 2

Expanded Workplace Empowerment Model

Appendix C

Figure 3: Application of Kanter's Structural Empowerment Framework

Figure 3

Application of Kanter's Structural Empowerment Framework

Application of Kanter's Structural Empowerment framework

Appendix D**Table 1: CINAHL Database Search****Table 1***CINAHL Database Search*

Terms	Articles Retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Structural empowerment, satisfaction, and shared governance	3	0	3	2

Appendix E

Table 2: PubMed Database Search

Table 2

PubMed Database Search

Terms	Articles Retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Structural empowerment, satisfaction, and shared governance	5	0	5	5

Appendix F

Informational Flyer

Implementation of a unit-based council To Project Participant:

You are invited to participate in a research project by Dr. Taqialdeen Zami, DNP, RN, PMHNP-BC, and Tim Nguyen DNP, RN, AGACNP-BC, California State University, Los Angeles. In this study, we hope to learn more about how a unit-based council will affect the perception of structural empowerment. All staff nurses (full-time, part-time, and per diem) are invited to participate in this study through a recruitment flyer and convenience sampling method. We hope our research will increase perceptions of structural empowerment in the workplace. There are no procedures conducted in this research project.

Participants will be asked to complete a survey pre-and post-implementation of the unit-based council. The Conditions for Workplace Effectiveness Questionnaire (CWEQ) measures the concept of structural empowerment. There are 6 subscales which are defined as access to opportunity, access to resources, access to information, access to support, formal powers, and informal powers. The survey will be fully anonymous. Participants will have the option to not answer any questions that may make them feel uncomfortable. Each participant is asked to complete the survey within an hour. There will be no compensation for participation in this study.

The risk involved is an inconvenience of the participant's time. We understand that each participant's time is valuable, and surveys take time to complete. Participants are able to withdraw from the study at any time.

Reports resulting from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law. If you choose to participate, we will protect your confidentiality. The surveys are completely anonymous without any identifying information and are stored in the critical care director's locked office. The principal investigator, co-investigator, and critical care directors will have access to the surveys. Participants can withdraw from the study at any time prior to the completion of the survey. The surveys will be stored for a minimum of three years following the completion of the study. The protection of confidentiality is our priority.

Any surveys that are not anonymous will be withdrawn and returned to the participant and not used in the study. We expect to have an estimated 15 participants in the pre-and post-survey. Once the survey is completed, study results will be available for the participants if they chose to inquire.

If you have any questions about this research, please call Dr. Taqialdeen Zami, DNP, RN, PMHNP-BC at (323) 343-4700 or write him at TZamil@calstatela.edu, 5151 State University Dr. Los Angeles, CA 90032. Tim Nguyen at (213) 304-0800 or write him at tim.nguyen-813@csu.fullerton.edu

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix G

Conditions for Work Effectiveness Questionnaire-I

CONDITIONS FOR WORK EFFECTIVENESS QUESTIONNAIRE-I

How much of each kind of opportunity do you have in your present job?

	1 = None	2	3 = Some	4	5 = A Lot			
1. Challenging work				1	2	3	4	5
2. The chance to gain new skills and knowledge on the job				1	2	3	4	5
3. Access to training programs for learning new things				1	2	3	4	5
4. The chance to learn how the hospital works				1	2	3	4	5
5. Tasks that use all of your own skills and knowledge				1	2	3	4	5
6. The chance to advance to better jobs				1	2	3	4	5
7. The chances to assume different roles not related to current job				1	2	3	4	5

How much access to information do you have in your present job?

	1 = No Knowledge	2	3 = Some Knowledge	4	5 = Know A Lot			
1. The current state of the hospital				1	2	3	4	5
2. The relationship of the work of your unit to the hospital				1	2	3	4	5
3. How other people in positions like yours do their work				1	2	3	4	5
4. The values of top management				1	2	3	4	5

5. The goals of top management	1	2	3	4	5
6. This year's plan for your work unit	1	2	3	4	5
7. How salary decisions are made for people in positions like yours	1	2	3	4	5
8. What other departments think of your unit	1	2	3	4	5

How much access to support do you have in your present job?

1 = None	2	3 = Some	4	5 = A Lot	
1. Specific information about things you do well	1	2	3	4	5
2. Specific comments about things you could improve	1	2	3	4	5
3. Helpful hints or problem-solving advice	1	2	3	4	5
4. Information or suggestions about job possibilities	1	2	3	4	5
5. Discussion of further training or education	1	2	3	4	5
6. Help when there is a work crisis	1	2	3	4	5
7. Help in gaining access to people who can get the job done	1	2	3	4	5
8. Help in getting materials and supplies needed to get the job done	1	2	3	4	5
9. Rewards and recognition for a job well done	1	2	3	4	5

How much access to resources do you have in your present job?

1 = None	2	3 = Some	4	5 = A Lot			
1. Having supplies necessary for the job			1	2	3	4	5
2. Time available to do necessary paperwork			1	2	3	4	5
3. Time available to accomplish job requirements			1	2	3	4	5
4. Acquiring temporary help when needed			1	2	3	4	5
5. Influencing decisions about obtaining human resources (permanent) for your unit.			1	2	3	4	5
6. Influencing decisions about obtaining supplies for your unit			1	2	3	4	5
7. Influencing decisions about obtaining equipment for your unit			1	2	3	4	5

**In my work setting/job:
(JAS)**

1 = None	2	3 = Some	4	5 = A Lot			
1. the amount of variety in tasks associated with my job is			1	2	3	4	5
2. the rewards for unusual performance on the job are			1	2	3	4	5
3. the rewards for innovation on the job are			1	2	3	4	5
4. the amount of flexibility in my job is			1	2	3	4	5

5. the number of approvals needed for nonroutine decisions are	1	2	3	4	5
6. the relation of tasks in my job to current problem areas of the organization is	1	2	3	4	5
7. my amount of participation in educational programs is	1	2	3	4	5
8. my amount of participation in problem solving task forces is	1	2	3	4	5
9. the amount of visibility of my work-related activities within the institution is	1	2	3	4	5

**How much opportunity do you have for these activities in your present job:
(ORS)**

	1 = None	2	3 = Some	4	5 = A Lot
1. Collaborating on patient care with physicians	1	2	3	4	5
2. Receiving helpful feedback from physicians	1	2	3	4	5
3. Being sought out by physicians for patient information	1	2	3	4	5
4. Receiving recognition by physicians	1	2	3	4	5
5. Having physicians ask for your opinion	1	2	3	4	5
6. Being sought out by supervisor for ideas about ward management issues	1	2	3	4	5
7. Having immediate supervisor ask for your opinion	1	2	3	4	5
8. Receiving early information of upcoming changes in work unit from your immediate supervisor	1	2	3	4	5

9. chances to increase your influence outside your unit e.g., nomination to influential committees by supervisor	1	2	3	4	5
10. Seeking out ideas from auxiliary workers on the unit, e.g., secretaries, ward clerks, housekeeping.	1	2	3	4	5
11. Getting to know auxiliary workers as people	1	2	3	4	5
12. Seeking out ideas from auxiliary workers outside of the unit, e.g., admission clerks, technicians	1	2	3	4	5
13. Being sought out by peers for information	1	2	3	4	5
14. Receiving helpful feedback from peers	1	2	3	4	5
15. Having peers ask your opinion on patient care issues	1	2	3	4	5
16. Being sought out by peers for help with problems	1	2	3	4	5
17. Exchanging favours with peers	1	2	3	4	5
18. Seeking out ideas from professionals other than physicians, e.g., physiotherapists, occupational therapists, dieticians	1	2	3	4	5

Appendix H

Organizational Approval Letter

Performance Improvement vs. Research Determination Form

Name of Individual Completing Form:

Date:

Principal Investigator (if different than above):

Principal Investigator Job Title:

Title of Project:

The purpose of this form is to help determine if a proposed project should be considered performance improvement or research. This form should be completed by the Principal Investigator, Project Leader, Partnership Council Chair or New Knowledge representative prior initiating a new project. Performance Improvement (PI) is the process whereby quality of care can be monitored and improved.

PI uses scientific methodology to improve performance. Performance can be measured in terms of clinical outcomes, patient satisfaction, error rates, productivity and other metrics. Results are used *locally* to improve care by improving the process being monitored. Complete this form and submit to the Clinical Trials Department to verify that you will be conducting a PI effort and that it currently does not meet the definition of human research.

1. Does this project involve any of the following (check all that apply):

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Investigational Drug or Device | <input type="checkbox"/> A fixed clinical protocol that may not be altered by caregivers and staff |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Randomizing patients | <input type="checkbox"/> A non PIH Health site |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Objectives other than producing an improvement in safety or care. | |

If any of the above are checked, then this project cannot be approved as a PI project, and must be submitted and approved by the Research Oversight Committee (ROC) as a Research Protocol before it can move forward.

XX None of the above, continue and complete form.

2. Which of the following best describes the process that is being evaluated?

XX The process is currently the standard of care (evidenced based)

The process is not currently the standard of care, and is prospectively being evaluated compared to the current standard of care (no current evidence to support proposed process)

3. What is the purpose statement of this project? (description of proposed project)

Describe: The purpose of the project is to create and implement a unit-based council in the critical care department at PIH Good Samaritan Hospital

4. Please list the outcome measures being collected as part of the effort:

Please List: Nursing satisfaction scores will be the outcome measures

5. Please describe the location and/or patient population being evaluated by the project:

Describe: ICU nurses at PIH Good Samaritan Hospital

6. Please describe your data collection plan and methodology:

a) What is the process by which the quality data will be collected and analyzed? The nurses will be asked to complete an anonymous survey. The survey titled "Conditions for Work Effectiveness" (CWEQ) is a likert scale assessing level of empowerment in the work place.

b) How will the process be evaluated? The CWEQ survey scores will be tallied. There will be a pre and post implementation survey. Will it be revised based on that analysis? The survey will not be revised.

c) How often will this same collection/analysis process sequence be repeated?

Describe: The survey will be provided before the implementation of the Unit-based council and 2 months after the council is effective.

7. At what point will this project be terminated (i.e.: at what point will your outcome measures indicate that the "quality" of the process is sufficient)?

Describe: The project will conclude after 2 months.

8. Is there any data being collected that is not part of the effort?

No

Yes, please List:

9. Is this project being funded?

No

Yes, please indicate the funding source:

10. At this time, do you have any intention to publish or present the information gathered outside of PIH Health?

No

Yes (requires approval from the Research Oversight Committee. Requires additional approval from marketing if PIH name will be disclosed)

Please Note:

This project meets the criteria of being a PI project. *approved.*

This project will need to be taken to the Research Oversight Committee for further review.

- This project does not meet the criteria of being a PI project, the Clinical Trials Research Nurse will generate a letter instructing the investigator to resubmit the project as a research protocol and it will need to be taken to the Research Oversight Committee.

Rose Douglas
Print/ Sign/ Date 6/14/2022
Clinical Trials Research Representative

Sarah Merkle
Print/ Sign/ Date 6/14/2022
New Knowledge Representative

Appendix I
IRB Approval Letter

Office Memorandum

DATE:	November 30, 2022
TO:	Taqialdeen Zamil, DNP
FROM:	LaTreshia Scott
PROJECT TITLE:	[1956012-1] Implementation of a unit-based council
REFERENCE #:	22-14X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	November 30, 2022
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category # 2(i)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact LaTreshia Scott. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

Appendix J

Figure 4: Mean Comparisons of Structural Empowerment Scores

Figure 4

Mean Comparisons of Structural Empowerment Scores

Appendix K

Table 3: Two-tailed Paired *t*-test Difference

Table 3

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-test for the Difference Between December 2022 and February 2023

December_2022		February_2023		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
2.55	0.74	3.11	0.64	-11.33	< .001	1.49

Note. N = 58. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 57. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Appendix L

Figure 4: Mean Difference of Total Empowerment Scores

Figure 4

Mean Differences of December 2022 and February 2023 with 95.00% CI Error Bars